

A social link based private storage cloud

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Abstract—In this paper, we present O^3 , a social link based private storage cloud for decentralized collaboration. O^3 allows users to share and collaborate on collections of files (shared folders) with others, in a decentralized manner, without the need for intermediaries (such as public cloud storage servers) to intervene. Thus, users can keep their working relationships (who they work with) and what they work on private from third parties. Using benchmarks and traces from real workloads, we experimentally evaluate O^3 and demonstrate that the system scales linearly when synchronizing increasing numbers of concurrent users, while performing on-par with the ext4 non-version-tracking filesystem.

Index Terms—Private Storage Cloud, Distributed File Systems, Replication, File sharing, Synchronization

I. INTRODUCTION

Today, naming, addressing, and most of the Internet services that critically affect users’ lives are in the hands of a few large, centralized, and typically, corporate entities. One critical Internet service with a profound impact on users’ lives is that of data storage. A number of popular cloud storage providers exists that offer features such as storage, anytime-anywhere access, and automated file synchronization and storage maintenance (e.g., [1], [2], [3], [4]). While convenient, these services come with a critical privacy cost. To obtain service, users inevitably hand over to the service provider access to personal information including a subset (or all) of their private data collections, or/and information about their social and working relationships with other users.

There is an alarming rise in the number of incidents from major cloud storage providers involving data leakage, data loss, intentional deletion of user files, and systematic sifting and analysis of user data for commercial benefit (e.g., [5], [6], [7], [8], [9], [10]). As a result, there have been growing calls from researchers and society at large in favor of “re-decentralizing” the Internet, taking its services out of the hands of large corporate entities. This work is a step in this direction.

In this paper, we present the “On Our Own” (O^3) social link-based private storage cloud. O^3 allows users to share collections of files (shared folders) with others, in a decentralized manner, without the need for intermediaries (such as public cloud storage servers) to intervene. Thus, users can keep their relationships with other users (who they socialize and work with) and their activities (what they share and what they work on) private from third parties.

O^3 provides a uniform POSIX interface for legacy applications accessing both a user’s shared folders as well as her private (non-shared) folders. Users can partially replicate any subset of their data collections (shared or non-shared) on their

devices of choice. Thus, O^3 can be used by users to holistically manage their entire cross-device data collections. To this end, the system provides a global view of all of a user’s files, regardless of whether they are stored locally or not, and can fetch files on demand from other devices owned by the user, or in the case of shared files, from other users’ devices.

We summarize the contributions of this paper as follows. We present the design of the O^3 private storage cloud for private, decentralized collaboration. Users can work at leisure on files while the system 1) seamlessly tracks all changes that users make to files, 2) automates the synchronization of replicated files across users and their devices, and 3) detects and helps users resolve conflicts via 3-way merge that arise from concurrent updates made when devices are offline. O^3 achieves this with a synchronization protocol and algorithms based on novel data structures called “epoch-graphs” that enable the system to track and propagate changes to files and enforce causality-preserving replay of these changes across all devices of all users. The protocol, algorithms, and epoch graphs are carefully designed to respect user privacy; they intentionally hide information about a user and her work habits, such as the number of devices the user owns and the user’s rate of work (e.g., updates made) on files she has not shared with others. The system provides seamless treatment of both a user’s shared as well as her private, non-shared files distributed across her personal devices. Finally, using benchmarks and traces from real workloads, we experimentally evaluate O^3 and demonstrate that the system scales linearly when synchronizing increasing numbers of concurrent users, while performing on-par with the ext4 non-version-tracking filesystem.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We assume a system consisting of multiple users. Each user defines her set of personal devices, which communicate to synchronize her whole data collection. Users create shares and communicate with other users, that participate in the same share, to synchronize only shared data elements. A node in O^3 refers to a device d owned by a user u . For intra group communication we assume a node is identified by the tuple $\langle deviceID, address \rangle$, while for inter group communication by the tuple $\langle userID, address \rangle$. Each node is equipped with a FIFO *input message queue*, that stores all messages delivered to it along with the id of the sender. The node loops fetching one message at a time from the input message queue and invoking the corresponding message handler, passing the

message and the source node as parameters. Each node may synchronize concurrently with multiple nodes, either within the personal or the shared part of data collection.

The network is asynchronous and during pairwise communications can drop, delay, duplicate, or deliver messages out of order. However, we assume that messages are eventually delivered, provided that the corresponding senders keep on re-transmitting them. For all nodes, we make no assumptions regarding processor speeds. We assume authenticated channels, where the receiver of a message can always identify its sender. We assume the adversary does not have the computational power to violate the security of any underlying cryptographic primitives. We do not assume byzantine behaviour for O^3 . Specifically for any node that acts as a relay (transmitting data created by other nodes), we assume that it transmits data as received.

III. SYSTEM OVERVIEW

O^3 is a distributed, multi-user, multi-device per user, file system. O^3 allows users to:

- 1) manage, replicate, and synchronize data across their own devices,
- 2) share subsets of their data with other users, work independently on the shared files, and synchronize in an ad-hoc manner, i.e., work in an offline fashion,

O^3 manages replication of items using Replication Rules, and assists the user in resolving the conflicts that occur when multiple users work on the same file at different devices.

O^3 is a POSIX-compliant file system that allows unmodified applications to run on top of it. It tracks the versions of files as they change, upon every file-system close event, and manages these versions in version graphs. If conflicts arise, it uses these version graphs to present all “current” versions of a file to the user, using a different “decorated” name for each. The user can further edit any of these versions and select one of them as the resolution of the conflict, using an O^3 -specific tool.

Figure 1: Communication of O^3 components when accessing the contents of a file.

Figure 2: Communication of O^3 components during the execution of $EGSync$ and Replication Rules Enforcer, between Alice at device X and Bob at device Y.

O^3 supports partial replication of file content, by allowing the user to define Replication Rules. Each such rule addresses a subset of her data collection and declares the devices that should store the content of matching files. The system enforces these rules automatically.

O^3 consists of the following major subsystems:

- 1) A Metadata Store (*MS*), which tracks all object metadata, such as name, location, timestamps, etc.
- 2) A Content Store (*CS*), which manages file content in a copy-on-write manner.
- 3) A Replication Rules Enforcer subsystem, that applies the rules by identifying missing content, fetching it, and storing it in the *CS*.
- 4) A Synchronization subsystem that fully replicates the *MS*.
- 5) A POSIX-compliant file system that provides the interface to O^3 for user-space applications.
- 6) An asynchronous communications layer that integrates device management, user-to-user communications, and presence notifications, forming a Decentralized Connectivity Service (*DCS*) between devices of collaborating users.

In Figure 1 we present the subsystems’ interaction when accessing a file’s data, and in Figure 2 we present the subsystems’ interaction when synchronizing data and metadata.

O^3 works as depicted in Figure 3. User-level applications issue POSIX filesystem calls which O^3 intercepts. To create a new file, it first routes file create and write requests to the *CS* where actual file data are stored. Upon file close, O^3 obtains a *Content Identifier (Cid)* from the *CS* and registers it along with the remaining file metadata at the *MS* (as O^3 tracks one version for each file close). To service directory queries, it uses exclusively the *MS*, which stores all file metadata, including directory contents. The *MS* is fully replicated across all the user’s devices, and thus directory queries return the same results at any device, provided that devices are fully synchronized. Devices partially replicate the contents of the *CS*, based on user-defined *Replication Rules*.

Figure 3: Overview of interactions between O^3 components for creating a new file and obtaining the directory contents.

As an example of replication rules, imagine a scenario with a user owning a desktop and laptop computer, and a mobile phone. The user can specify that all files under the folder *Documents* are replicated everywhere, files under *Pictures* are replicated at the desktop and the laptop, while files under the folder *Videos* are only placed on her desktop computer, where the hard disk is big enough to store them. O^3 includes all files from the user’s collection in directory listings, and allows the user to access any picture from her mobile phone, even if it is not currently there, by bringing it from the desktop or the laptop on demand, if a connection is available.

The synchronization of the *MS* is frequent in an attempt to minimize conflicts. However, conflicts can still arise because of disconnected operation of devices. In the case of O^3 , which tracks per object histories, there are two types of conflicts. The first, which we call an *object conflict*, occurs when an object’s (file’s or directory’s) attributes and/or content are modified at more than one device concurrently. The second one is the *cross-object naming conflict*, which happens when the user assigns the same name, in the same directory, to different objects (files or directories). In any of the above cases, O^3 keeps track of the history of every object, and provides the user with the different versions, along with their common parent, allowing for a three-way merge.

Finally, the user is able to instruct the system to “forget” selected versions of a file, or forget a file completely. This functionality provides a means to clean up space in the content store, and reduce the size of the stored metadata.

In the next section, we will present O^3 in detail. Note that the *MS* repository, the Replication Rules Enforcer, the *CS* and the *FS* are adaptations of the corresponding ones in [11].

IV. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

A. Metadata Store

The *Metadata Store (MS)*, is the subsystem that manages metadata for O^3 . By metadata, we denote the file and directory names and their associated attributes, such as permissions, timestamps, owner, and group.

1) *Objects and Version Graphs*: The interface the *MS* provides is the following:

- `newObject(type)`: creates a new object
- `newVersion(Oid, Set<Metadata>)`: creates a new version for a specific object, with the specified metadata
- `getVersions(Oid) -> list<Versions>`: provides all versions of an object, along with their metadata
- `lookup(query) -> list<Versions>`: provides all versions of any object, that match the query

The *MS* manages five types of objects: a) the *directory* object, which maintains information about a directory in the file system, b) the *file* object, which maintains information about a file in the file system, c) the *symbolic link* object, which maintains information about a standard symbolic link to a file name, d) the *replication rule* object, which specifies where the content of files under a directory are replicated, and e) the *snapshot* object, which stores information about a snapshot (explained later in this section).

Each object in the *MS* is identified by a globally unique *Object Identifier (Oid)*. Each object consists of one or more versions, each one identified by a globally unique *Version Identifier (Vid)*. For each version of an object, the *MS* maintains a set of attributes. For example, for a file’s version, the *MS* maintains the *Oid* of the directory hosting this version, the file’s name, size, permissions, modification date, owner, group, and the *Cid* of its content. The *Cid* is the Content Identifier, assigned by the Content Store (*CS*), to each file content it manages.

The *MS* records *Objects* and their *versions*, by maintaining a directed acyclic version graph (DAG) for each object. File objects, because of content changes, may have a rich and deep version graph. An example of a version graph of a `file` object is depicted in Figure 4a.

In this graph we see one root version, with no parents (A1), and any subsequent version having one or more parents. At *fork* nodes, such as A2 and B2, we have multiple versions with the same parent; these denote concurrent modifications of the same version across different devices. *Trunk* nodes, such as B1, are nodes with no siblings, and denote points in the version graph with no conflicts. Leaf nodes in the graph represent the currently “active” versions (i.e., C3). A single leaf node is the normal case, for an object without conflicts. Multiple leaf nodes denote the conflicting active versions of an object (i.e., C3 and D1 in Figure 4b). Their nearest common ancestor (A1) is what O^3 provides as a “common parent” node for three-way merges.

Conflicts for a specific file are “welcome,” as they simply extend the version graph accordingly. Because versions are

Figure 4: Directed Acyclic Graphs of object versions. Yellow (lighter) nodes are “trunk” nodes, having no siblings and representing points in time with no forks. Green (darker) nodes are “fork” nodes. In the node identifiers, the letter denotes the device and the number the version number. Levels are assigned by Algorithm 1. Figure 4b depicts the graph of Figure 4a after adding a new fork node D1 and having its levels reassigned.

immutable, the *MS* offers the information of all previous ones at all times. Due to the copy-on-write approach of the *CS* (see Section IV-C), the content corresponding to any version is also always accessible.

2) *Leveling algorithm*: O^3 utilizes a novel *level-ranking* algorithm presented in Algorithm 1, to assign a level to each node in an object’s version graph. The assigned level aids in conflict management, by providing a means to quickly identify the nearest trunk node and present it as the common parent of conflicting versions (see Section IV-D). Algorithm 1 assigns to the root node of an object a level of one, to each trunk node the level of its parent(s) increased by one, and ensures that all fork nodes have the level of their common parent also increased by one. Each time a fork node is inserted in the version graph, all versions with higher level, if they exist, are reassigned to the same level. For example, suppose that in the graph of Figure 4a a new child of version A1, node D1, is inserted (due to synchronization with device D). This would create a new fork (unresolved conflict), as depicted in Figure 4b. As a consequence, all versions below A1 are reassigned to level 2, resulting in a graph with only two levels, and with two leaves: nodes C3 and D1.

We physically store the version graph with the reverse direction of Figure 4a, i.e., with edges directed from the leaves to the root. When finished, Algorithm 1 ensures all fork nodes have the same level L , while their parent, which is always a trunk node, has level $L-1$. The proof that above any level that is a fork segment there is always a level with a single trunk node is trivial. If level N is a fork segment (with more than one nodes, and thus not a single trunk node), and if level $N-1$ is also a fork segment, then we will show that $N = N-1$ must hold, which is impossible. The reason that N must be equal to $N-1$ is because either: a) nodes of N would be assigned level $N-1$ if the fork of level $N-1$ already existed when nodes of level N were created (lines 9–10), or b) the nodes of N would be reassigned to level $N-1$ if the fork at $N-1$ was created after N was assigned (lines 12–14). Note that, the root node is always a trunk node, as it is created on

a single device (no two devices can create an object with the same *oid*, as the latter is unique across the devices of the group).

The algorithm is $O(1)$ in the common cases of adding versions to a version graph with no conflicts (lines 2–5), and when adding one more fork node at the highest-leveled fork segment (lines 9–10). If a fork node is added above that, our algorithm will reassign the level at all nodes below the currently added one (lines 12–14), which is more costly.

Algorithm 1 Level Ranking Algorithm

```

1: procedure ASSIGNLEVEL(version, graph):
2:   if len(version.parents) == 0 then                                ▷ root node
3:     version.level = 1
4:   else if version.parents == graph.leaves then                    ▷ trunk node
5:     version.level = parents[0].level + 1
6:   else                                                                ▷ fork node
7:     minParentLevel = version.locateMinParentLevel()
8:     trunk = graph.locateLatestTrunkNode(minParentLevel)
9:     if minParentLevel > trunk.level then                            ▷ one more...
10:      version.level = minParentLevel                                ▷ ...fork node
11:   else                                                                ▷ new conflict, reassign levels at subsequent nodes
12:     toUpdate = graph.findAll(level > trunk.level)
13:     for each V in toUpdate do
14:       V.level = trunk.level + 1

```

3) *Metadata Store Components*: The *MS* consists logically of two components: the *metadata repository*, and the *update log*. The *metadata repository* is search-optimized and is used to respond to `lookup()` requests. It stores all objects created by the *MS* interface, and all *Cids* along with the devices that store them. The *update log* records all metadata update actions that are applied to the *metadata repository*, in the order they happened. It is fully replicated across devices, and frequently shrunk by removing old regions that are guaranteed to be replicated across all devices in the group. Each node that receives it, replays it in an order that preserves *causality*, and is guaranteed to obtain the same (or an equivalent) metadata repository.

We design the *MS update log* (See Section III) around a novel data structure called *Epoch Graph* (*EG*). When a user

performs a file system update operation (e.g. edit, delete, rename), O^3 generates a new version in the corresponding object’s version graph. Additionally, O^3 registers a pointer to this version in an *epoch*, a structure that stores all versions generated during a specific period of time. An epoch is identified by a globally unique identifier Eid . In our current design, the Eid comprises a tuple $\langle userID, deviceID, tag \rangle$, where the $userID$ and $deviceID$ identify the user and device that created the epoch, and the tag uniquely identifies the epoch within this device. Each device maintains a “current” epoch to record new versions as they occur, which it closes at intervals determined locally. Finally, an epoch E has a dependency list P of other “parent” epochs; all object versions recorded at each epoch p in P are incorporated into the *metadata repository*, before epoch E is closed.

Figure 5 depicts a Private EG, which is the EG O^3 uses to record non-shared objects. The first epoch node in the Private EG is the root epoch, which is an empty epoch with a well known identifier; each user’s device initializes its copy of the Private EG with this node, and creates a new “current” epoch ready to record local *MS* repository changes (i.e. object update operations). EG grows over time as devices learn about each other’s (potentially concurrent) epochs via synchronization sessions.

Figure 5: A sample epoch graph depicting concurrency between different devices of a user. Devices A and B synchronized immediately after epoch A2, and then worked in isolation until epoch A5, which was closed after device A incorporated epoch B2 created at device B.

When a device closes its current epoch E (e.g., when a synchronization event occurs), it sets the dependency list P of E to the current leaves of the Private EG, and thus E becomes the new, sole leaf of the Private EG. This creates a single rooted, directed, acyclic graph of epochs, which we store with both directions. Additionally, we store $Eids$ in a dictionary, allowing random access to any node in the graph.

O^3 supports sharing of files across users at the granularity of folders. A *share* is a folder the user selects to collaborate on with others. The folder may have an initial set of objects in it, and grow as users collaborate and add to it over time. For every *share*, there is a separate, independent epoch graph. Thus, the *update log* includes the Private EG and a separate EG for each *share* in which the user participates.

Any user can create a *share* locally at any of her devices, selecting its participants. Then O^3 performs the following:

- It creates a new Share EG, along with its root epoch.
- It creates a *share* object, which contains the Sid (a globally unique identifier, which contains $\langle userID, deviceID, tag \rangle$), the *share*’s root Eid , and the list of users participating in the *share*. Then, it records this object in the current epoch of the Private EG, so that the remaining personal devices of the user eventually learn about the *share*, during subsequent synchronization sessions.
- For each file system object that already exists in the folder to share, the system “obsoletes” it and creates a “shallow” copy of its leaf versions into a new object, thus guaranteeing that the pre-existing version history is not exposed to the other users participating in the *share*. “Obsoleting” an object is actually a deletion event, where a new version is created at its version graph with parents all current leaves; this deletion event is marked in the Private EG. The new object, which contains copies of the leaf versions of the obsoleted one (along with their common parent in case of conflict), is registered in the root epoch of the *share*’s EG.

The *share*’s creator (e.g. Alice) notifies out-of-band the participating users (e.g. Bob) with the Sid and the list of participants. With this information, Bob is able to mount the *share* and fetch its data from any participant’s device. During mount, O^3 creates a local copy of the *share* definition in Bob’s Private EG and creates a new EG for the data of the *share*.

Epochs are a means to synchronize the *MS* repository across devices, as further explained in Section IV-B below. They are efficient storage-wise, as they are simply an ordered list of $\langle Oid, Vid \rangle$ tuples. Nonetheless, they are often garbage collected to preserve space. For the user’s private EG, an epoch E is discarded when every device reports an epoch with a path towards E . For a *share* EG, an epoch E at a user U ’s device is discarded when every device of U **and** at least one device of every other user participating in the *share*, reports an epoch with a path towards E .

This design, along with the synchronization protocol, simplifies metadata replication, by completely avoiding *update log* conflicts during metadata synchronization.

B. Synchronization Protocol

O^3 replicates the *MS* repository using the EG data structure and the two-phase Epoch Graph Synchronization (*EGSync*) protocol. An O^3 device initiates an *EGSync* instance to obtain the epochs of another device’s EG (either the Private or a *Share*-specific one). Figure 6 provides a UML sequence diagram of the protocol between Alice and Bob. Note that the identifiers Sid and Eid in Figure 6 are actually tuples $\langle userID, etag \rangle$ where $etag$ is the encrypted $\langle deviceID, tag \rangle$ described in Section IV-A3. The personal devices of a user share a key, which they use to encrypt private portions of each identifier they expose to other users. This choice allows the system to hide both the cardinality of a user’s personal device group (by hiding device ids), as well as counters used

to produce identifiers, that would expose the progress made by the user on objects outside the share.

Figure 6: A UML sequence diagram of *EGSync*.

1) *Notation*: For the rest of this document consider the following:

- We refer to Epoch Graph of user X for share S as EG_{X_S} .
- We refer to Epoch Graph of user X for share S simply as EG_X , in the context of a single share S.
- When stating that node A discovers an epoch e of node B missing from EG_A , we mean that A obtains the *Eid* of epoch e , that exists in EG_B and does not exist in EG_A .

2) *Data Structures*: Each node maintains in memory data structures during the execution of the protocol. In this section we describe those structures, which are used by the algorithm of *EGSync*. All data structures are indexed by *shareID*, which we omit for brevity.

- *requestedEpochs*: set of *epochID*.
During a synchronization session, a node may have missing epochs. Each missing epoch that is requested is inserted in this map to avoid re-requesting it from another node.
- *RNAEpochs*: $epochID \mapsto data$.
(Received but Not Applied epochs)

Upon receiving an epoch during a synchronization session it is added to this map (of the Received but Not Applied epochs). When all dependencies of an epoch in *RNAEpochs* exist in *EG*, then the epoch's operations are executed in the *MS*, the epoch is added in *EG* and removed from *RNAEpochs*. Note that due to asynchronous synchronization's design, a node may receive an epoch before its dependent epochs (parents in the epoch graph).

- *ActiveTargets*: set of *nodeID*
We use this structure to avoid multiple concurrent synchronization sessions for the same topic (*shareID*) with the same node.

- *LISessions*: $sessionID \mapsto \langle \text{set of } epochID, timeoutID, newCK \rangle$.

(Locally Initiated sessions).

Upon protocol initiation, a node maintains the active and locally initiated synchronization sessions, to validate the existence of an active synchronization session when receiving protocol's messages. Moreover, the requested epochs per session are maintained to identify the end of a session, and to update *requestedEpochs* data structure, in case that the remote party becomes unreachable. *newCK* is used when aborting a session and starting a new one. (Section IV-B4).

- *RISessions*: $sessionID \mapsto node$.
(Remotely Initiated sessions).

Upon receiving a *SessionInit* message we store the session information in this structure. We use this structure to validate the existence of an active synchronization session, when receiving following protocol's messages.

- *PSessions*: $node \mapsto token$.
(Postponed sessions).

A synchronization session may be postponed due to the existence of an active session with the same node for the same *shareID*. This could happen in cases such as the Feedback session. (IV-B6)

Note that each entry in *requestedEpochs*, *LISessions* and *RISessions* data structures also contain a timeout value. These timeout values are used to clean up data structures in case that a node has crashed; thus the protocol's state contains information only on active synchronization sessions.

3) *EGSync's First Phase - Missing Epoch Discovery*: Alice calls the **STARTSYNC** procedure to initiate a new session with user Bob (Figure 7). If no other session is active, she initiates a new synchronization session by sending a **SESSIONINIT** message with current knowledge *CK*, which is the set of *Eids* of the leaves of EG_{Alice} , as recorded in her current device. *CK* is necessary for Bob to efficiently locate the epochs in EG_{Bob} missing from EG_{Alice} . Bob uses Algorithm 2 to produce *PNK*, which is the set of epochs potentially not known to (i.e., potentially missing from) EG_{Alice} .

In line 2, the algorithm detects if every epoch in the remote's (Alice's) current knowledge set (*RCK*) exists in the current (Bob's) device's *EG* (EG_{Bob}). If all epochs are found, it initializes a starting set *SS* with *RCK*. If however any

```

1: procedure STARTSYNC(target, token)
2:   if target  $\in$  ActiveTargets then
3:     PSessions[target]  $\leftarrow$  token return
4:     sessionID  $\leftarrow$  createSessionID(token)
5:     CK  $\leftarrow$  getLeaves()
6:     isFeedBack  $\leftarrow$  (token = "FEEDBACK")
7:     send SESSIONINIT (sessionID, CK, isFeedBack) to target.addr
8:     tID  $\leftarrow$  setTimeout(t1, IPHASE1( sessionID, target))
9:     LISessions[sessionID]  $\leftarrow$   $\langle \emptyset, tID \rangle$ 
10:    ActiveTargets  $\leftarrow$  ActiveTargets  $\cup$  target

```

Figure 7: The STARTSYNC procedure is called to initiate a synchronization session. The *createSessionID* function creates a sessionID using the token supplied. The token is used by the initiator when finalizing the session. The *getLeaves* function returns a set with the eIDs of the leaves of EG. The *setTimeout* function registers a new timeout for the new session, with *t1* being the timeout value used during the first phase of the protocol.

```

1: procedure ON SESSIONINIT(sessionID, CK, isFeedBack) from source:
2:   EG  $\leftarrow$  getEpochGraph()
3:    $\langle SS, PNK, rknown \rangle \leftarrow$  PNKEPOCHS(EG, CK, source.userID)
4:   send POTENTIALLYMISSING ( sessionID, SS, PNK ) to
   source.addr
5:   tID  $\leftarrow$  setTimeout(t1, TPHASE1( sessionID, source))
6:   RISessions[sessionID]  $\leftarrow$  (source, tID)
7:   if  $\neg rknown \wedge \neg isFeedBack$  then
8:     PSessions[source]  $\leftarrow$  "FEEDBACK"

```

Figure 8: The handler of SESSIONINIT message. The *getEpochGraph* function returns the memory address of the EG.

epoch in *RCK* is missing, it initializes *SS* with the latest known epochs (line 8) created by Alice's devices, that Bob knows about. The latest known epochs of Alice are accessible because each device in O^3 maintains locally the latest known epochs for each user, which are updated when new epochs arrive during a synchronization session. Multiple latest known epochs for Alice may exist, if Alice worked concurrently across more than one of her devices.

Given *SS*, the algorithm locates the nearest trunk node (line 11), and starts descending EG_{Bob} towards the leaves, collecting all nodes it encounters in the *PNK* (function *descendants* in line 12). From this set it subtracts all nodes encountered in all paths from the starting set up to the nearest trunk that started the search, as at least one of Alice's devices already knows about them (function *ancestorsUntil*, in line 12). If the *RCK* is an empty set (line 3), then this node has no data for the share and this is its initial synchronization session; thus *PNK* is populated with all epochs of EG_{Bob} (line 5). For graph traversals, we use breadth-first search while memorizing visited nodes, to avoid repeated visits due to multi-parented nodes. These traversals are efficient, as EG is maintained using both directions and the complexity is proportional to the number of nodes between the entry and exit nodes of the traversal. This number grows when devices

```

1: procedure ON POTENTIALLYMISSING(sessionID, SS, PNK) from
   source:
2:    $\langle field1, tID, field3 \rangle \leftarrow$  LISessions[sessionID]
3:   cancelTimeout(tID)
4:   EG  $\leftarrow$  getEpochGraph()
5:    $\langle toRequest, sExists \rangle \leftarrow$  MISSINGEPOCHS(EG, requested,
   RNAEpochs, SS, PNK)
6:   if  $\neg sExists$  then
7:     newCK  $\leftarrow$  DISCOVERCK(EG, SS, PNK)
8:     tID  $\leftarrow$  setTimeout(t1, IPHASE1( sessionID, target))
9:     LISessions[sessionID]  $\leftarrow$   $\langle \emptyset, tID, newCK \rangle$ 
10:    send SESSIONABORT ( sessionID ) to source.addr
11:   else if toRequest =  $\emptyset$  then
12:     send NONETOREQUEST ( sessionID ) to source.addr
13:     LISessions  $\leftarrow$  LISessions - sessionID
14:     ActiveTargets  $\leftarrow$  ActiveTargets - target
15:   else
16:     send GETMISSING (toRequest) to source.addr
17:     requested  $\leftarrow$  requested  $\cup$  toRequest
18:     tID  $\leftarrow$  setTimeout(t2, IPHASE2( sessionID, source))
19:     LISessions[sessionID]  $\leftarrow$   $\langle$  sessionID, toRequest, tID  $\rangle$ 
20: procedure ON SESSIONABORTRECEIVED(sessionID) from source:
21:    $\langle field1, tID, newCK \rangle \leftarrow$  LISessions[sessionID]
22:   LISessions  $\leftarrow$  LISessions - sessionID
23:   newSessionID  $\leftarrow$  createSessionID(token)
24:   send SESSIONINIT (newSessionID, newCK) to source.addr
25:   tID  $\leftarrow$  setTimeout(t1, IPHASE1( newSessionID, target))
26:   LISessions[newSessionID]  $\leftarrow$   $\langle \emptyset, tID, newCK \rangle$ 

```

Figure 9: The handlers of POTENTIALLYMISSING, SESSIONABORTRECEIVED messages. The *cancelTimeout* function removes a registered timeout using its id. The value *t2*, used in *setTimeout*, is the timeout value used during the second phase of the protocol.

```

1: procedure ON SESSIONABORT(sessionID) from source:
2:    $\langle node, tID \rangle \leftarrow$  RISessions[sessionID]
3:   cancelTimeout(tID)
4:   RISessions  $\leftarrow$  RISessions - sessionID
5:   send SESSIONABORTRECEIVED ( sessionID ) to source.addr
6: procedure ON NONETOREQUEST(sessionID) from source:
7:    $\langle node, tID \rangle \leftarrow$  RISessions[sessionID]
8:   cancelTimeout(tID)
9:   RISessions  $\leftarrow$  RISessions - sessionID
10:  CHECKPOSTPONED(source)
11: procedure ON GETMISSING(sessionID, missing) from source:
12:    $\langle node, tID \rangle \leftarrow$  RISessions[sessionID]
13:   cancelTimeout(tID)
14:   EG  $\leftarrow$  getEpochGraph()
15:   for all eID  $\in$  missing do
16:     data  $\leftarrow$  getEpochData(EG, eID)
17:     send ( EPOCHDATA(sessionID, eID, data) ) to source.addr
18:   RISessions  $\leftarrow$  RISessions - sessionID
19:   CHECKPOSTPONED(source)
20: procedure CHECKPOSTPONED(target):
21:   if target  $\in$  PSessions.keys() then
22:     token  $\leftarrow$  PSessions[target]
23:     PSessions  $\leftarrow$  PSessions - target
24:     STARTSYNC(target, token)

```

Figure 10: The handlers of NONETOREQUEST, SESSIONABORT and GETMISSING messages, and the CHECKPOSTPONED function. The *getEpochData* function returns a set with all metadata updates occurred during the specified epoch.

```

1: procedure ON EPOCHDATA(sessionID, eID, data) from source:
2:    $\langle toReceive, tID \rangle \leftarrow LISessions[sessionID]$ 
3:    $toReceive \leftarrow toReceive - eID$ 
4:   if  $toReceive.length() = 0$  then
5:      $cancelTimeout(tID)$ 
6:      $LISessions \leftarrow LISessions - sessionID$ 
7:      $ActiveTargets \leftarrow ActiveTargets - source$ 
8:     CHECKPOSTPONED(source)
9:   else
10:     $resetTimeout(t2, tID)$ 
11:     $LISessions[sessionID] \leftarrow \langle toReceive, tID \rangle$ 
12:     $RNAEpochs[eID] \leftarrow data$ 
13:     $requested \leftarrow requested - eID$ 
14:     $EG \leftarrow getEpochGraph()$ 
15:    CHECKAPPLY( $EG, RNAEpochs, eID$ )

```

Figure 11: The handler of EPOCHDATA message.

```

1: procedure ON IPHASE1(sessionID, target):
2:    $LISessions \leftarrow LISessions - sessionID$ 
3:    $ActiveTargets \leftarrow ActiveTargets - target$ 
4:    $PSessions \leftarrow PSessions - target$ 

5: procedure ON IPHASE2(sessionID, target):
6:    $\langle toReceive, tID \rangle \leftarrow LISessions[sessionID]$ 
7:    $requested \leftarrow requested - toReceive$ 
8:    $LISessions \leftarrow LISessions - sessionID$ 
9:    $ActiveTargets \leftarrow ActiveTargets - target$ 
10:   $PSessions \leftarrow PSessions - target$ 
     $\triangleright$  Synchronize with another node of same share

11: procedure ON TPHASE1(sessionID, source):
12:   $RISessions \leftarrow RISessions - sessionID$ 
13:   $PSessions \leftarrow PSessions - source$ 

```

Figure 12: The handlers of session timeouts.

reduce the rate of synchronization, so a frequent rate should reduce the complexity.

Algorithm 2 Potentially not known epochs to Remote

```

1: function PNKEPOCHS( $EG, RCK, userID$ ):  $\triangleright$  RCK: remote CK
2:    $allKnown \leftarrow \forall e \in RCK : e \in EG$ 
3:    $SS \leftarrow \emptyset$   $\triangleright$  starting points for PNK search
4:   if  $RCK = \emptyset$  then  $\triangleright$  1st session ever for remote
5:      $PNK \leftarrow EG.root \cup descendants(EG.root)$ 
6:   else
7:     if  $\neg allKnown$  then
8:        $SS \leftarrow latestKnownEpochs(userID)$ 
9:     else
10:       $SS \leftarrow rCK$ 
11:       $trunk \leftarrow nearestTrunk(SS)$ 
12:       $PNK \leftarrow descendants(trunk) - ancestorsUntil(SS, trunk)$ 
return ( $PNK, SS, allKnown$ )

```

Bob follows the protocol by sending a **POTENTIALLYMISSING** message encapsulating the output of Algorithm 2. Upon receiving it, and using Algorithm 3, Alice’s device verifies that all epochs referenced in the SS exist in EG_{Alice} , by iterating over each and looking it up (lines 2 - 3). If any epoch is SS set does not exist, Alice responds with a **SESSIONABORT** message to terminate the current session (more information in section IV-B4). In the opposite case, the local device creates a $toRequest$ set with all epochs $e \in PNK : e \notin EG_{Alice} \wedge e \notin RNAEpochs \wedge e \notin requestedEpochs$ (lines 5 - 7 of Algorithm 3). At this point,

Alice discovers all epochs of EG_{Bob} missing from EG_{Alice} . In case $toRequest$ set is empty the synchronization session is completed with a **NONETOREQUEST** message (Figure 9, line 12), else the session continues to phase 2 (Section IV-B5).

Algorithm 3 Determine Missing Epochs

```

1: procedure MISSINGEPOCHS( $EG, requested, RNAEpochs, SS, PNK$ ):
2:   for each  $e \in SS$  do
3:     if  $e \notin EG$  then return ( $\emptyset, False$ )
4:    $toRequest \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
5:   for each  $e \in PNK$  do
6:     if  $e \notin EG \wedge e \notin requested \wedge e \notin RNAEpochs$  then
7:        $toRequest \leftarrow toRequest \cup e$ 
return ( $toRequest, True$ )

```

4) *Session Abort and Retry*: In case that any epoch of SS is not found, Alice cannot proceed with the current synchronization session and terminates it, by sending a **SESSIONABORT** message (Figure 9, line 10). This odd situation can happen when Alice chooses to work on a device that lags behind her own other devices in knowledge. However, using information from SS as reported by Bob, she can schedule a new session that starts at a higher point in the graph. To do this, she uses Algorithm 4. She iterates SS , as received by the **POTENTIALLYMISSING** message (line 3) to populate a known set of epochs K . The algorithm inserts in K each known epoch as is (line 5), whereas for any other epoch it first decodes the epoch identifier, to recover the device that created this epoch, and then retrieves the latest known epoch created by this device (line 7). This is possible because one of Alice’s devices has created epoch e , $\forall e \in SS$ (Algorithm 2, line 8) and all her devices can decode identifiers created inside her personal group. The latest known epochs of Alice’s devices are accessible because each device in O^3 also maintains locally the latest known epoch for each device of the local user and for each share, which are updated when new epochs arrive during a synchronization session. Finally, the algorithm returns the nearest trunk of K (line 7). The trunk is maintained in the $LISessions$ data structure (Figure 9, line 9), and, when receiving a **SESSIONABORTRECEIVED** message, it is used by $EGSync$ as the current knowledge CK to initiate a new synchronization session (Figure 9, line 24). This second iteration of protocol’s first phase leads to missing epochs’ discovery, as for each $e \in SS \wedge e \in EG_{Alice}$. With this approach, a device of Alice that lags behind her other own devices can catch up with information for this specific share from devices of other users.

Algorithm 4 Discover new CK

```

1: function DISCOVERCK( $EG, SS$ ):
2:    $K \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
3:   for each  $e \in SS$  do
4:     if  $e \in EG$  then
5:        $K \leftarrow K \cup e$ 
6:     else
7:        $K \leftarrow K \cup latestKnownEpoch(e.creator)$ 
return  $nearestTrunk(K)$ 

```

5) *EGSync's Second Phase - Missing Epoch Retrieval*: In the second phase of the protocol, *toRequest* set is requested via a **GETMISSING** message (Figure 9, line 16) and Bob's device replies with multiple **EPOCHDATA** messages (Figure 10, line 17), one for each requested epoch. The synchronization session is completed when Alice receives all requested epochs by Bob (Figure 11, line 4).

Algorithm 5 Check Applicability of received but not applied epoch

```

1: function CHECKAPPLY(EG, RNAEpochs, eID):
2:   for each  $e \in \text{RNAEpochs}[eID].\text{parents}$  do
3:     if  $e \notin \text{EG}$  then return
4:   EG.insert(eID, RNAEpochs[eID])
5:   RNAEpochs.delete(eID)
6:   for each  $eID \in \text{RNAEpochs.keys}()$  do
7:     checkapply(EG, RNAEpochs, eID)

```

To optimize the protocol's bit complexity we avoid requesting the same epoch from multiple devices. This is achieved in line 6 of Algorithm 3. This design choice in addition to the asynchronous synchronization's design may result in an epoch to be received before its dependencies (parent(s) in the EG). To guarantee the consistency semantics of O^3 we perform an applicability check for each received epoch (Figure 11, line 15) using Algorithm 5. Finally, to ensure liveness of the protocol, in case that a node is not responding we introduce timeouts for each phase and at each node. The timeout value defines the maximum amount of time among two incoming messages for a specified session. Specifically, for the second phase, an epoch is erased from the *requested* structure when the target node becomes unreachable, thus allowing requesting it again from another reachable node upon a following synchronization session.

6) *Feedback Session*: In Figure 6 we present an optional step for the protocol. When a user announces her current knowledge to another user to initiate a synchronization session, the remote user may discover epochs she does not possess (epochs in CK that does not exist in her EG). In such case, the remote user inserts an entry to *PSessions* structure for the specified node (Figure 8, line 8). This does not happen if the *isFeedback* flag is enabled, which means that the current session is actually a Feedback session, to avoid multiple synchronization sessions among two nodes that have been synchronized bio-directional.

When the remote node has sent all requested epochs (via **EPOCHDATA** messages), it will initiate a new session with the other node (in the opposite direction this time), if an entry exists in the *PSessions* structure. Using this mechanism both nodes synchronize each other.

7) *Protocol Proofs*: In this section we provide proofs, for the interested reader, that *EGSync* maintains the properties of safety and liveness.

a) *Concurrent Synchronization Sessions*: The system model of section II assumes that multiple concurrent synchronization session may exist. We use Lemmas 2 and 4 to show

that the protocol's state can handle concurrent synchronization sessions.

Lemma 1. *Consider a node A that participates in multiple shares and executes EGSync with multiple nodes. Concurrent access to the local state of node A, regarding concurrent protocol instances, is not possible.*

Proof. The state of a node A regarding the execution of *EGSync* consists of the data structures of section IV-B2. These are accessed upon receiving protocol messages and within protocol's message handlers, that according to system model in Section II are executed one at a time. As a result, concurrent access to the these structures is not possible. \square

Lemma 2. *Consider a node A that participates in multiple shares and executes EGSync. The execution of two concurrent protocol instances with nodes B and C, regarding shares S and S' respectively, with $S \neq S'$, is independent of each other.*

Proof. The state of a node A regarding the execution of *EGSync* consists of the data structures of section IV-B2. Concurrent access to the state is not possible due to Lemma 1. Moreover, all data structures are indexed by shareID, thus two concurrent protocol instances of node A, with nodes B and C, regarding shares S and S' respectively, with $S \neq S'$, are totally independent. \square

Lemma 3. *Consider two parties I (Initiator) and T (Target) that participate in share S and execute EGSync. Only one active protocol instance from I to T, regarding S, is allowed.*

Proof. In line 3 of Figure 7 a new protocol instance from I to T and regarding S is postponed if another one is active. Thus the Lemma holds. \square

Lemma 4. *Consider a node A that participates in share S and executes EGSync. The execution of two concurrent protocol instances with nodes B and C, and for share S is allowed.*

Proof. The state of a node A regarding the execution of *EGSync* consists of the data structures of section IV-B2. Concurrent access to the state is not possible due to Lemma 1.

The entries in data structures *LISession*, *RISessions*, *PSessions* and *ActiveTargets* are used only in the context of a single synchronization session. The first two are used to validate that incoming messages refer to active synchronization sessions and the remaining are used to to achieve the invariant of Lemma 3, and for the optional Feedback described in section IV-B6.

requestedEpochs is used to avoid requesting a single epoch e from multiple nodes, during concurrent synchronization sessions and for the same share S. *RNAEpochs* is used to store epochs that have been received, but are not applicable yet due to missing dependencies. In case A has requested an epoch e from B ($e \in \text{requestedEpochs}$), or in case A has already received an epoch e from B ($e \in \text{RNAEpochs}$), A will not request $e \in \text{EG}_C$ from C. This does not affect the

protocol instance of A with C, as A will discover, request and obtain the remaining epochs with C.

Thus concurrent protocol instances of a node A with nodes B and C for the same share S are allowed. \square

b) *Safety:*

Theorem 5. Consider a node A that uses O^3 , and constructs epoch graphs for the MS update log. An epoch graph has the following properties:

- 1) Epoch graph is single-rooted, connected, directed and acyclic.
- 2) The parents of an epoch $e \in EG$ form an immutable set.

Proof. Both properties hold due to the construction process of epoch graphs, as described in Section IV-A3:

- 1) **Single-root:** When A mounts O^3 for the first time, it creates the root epoch re for the *private epoch graph*. When A creates a share S , it also creates a new epoch graph for S , along with its root epoch re_s . Thus, an epoch graph, either the *private* or a *shared* has a single root.

Connected & directed: In case the root epoch is the single epoch of an epoch graph, it is also its single leaf. When A inserts an epoch e in EG, it connects e with directed edges from each $l, l \in L$ towards e , where L is the set of leaves of EG. Thus, EG is connected and directed from root towards leaves.

Acyclic: A creates edges only from leaves towards a new epoch e , when inserting e in EG, and, then, e is the new leaf of EG. In this way, it is not possible to create an outgoing edge from an epoch e towards an epoch a , where a has been inserted in EG before e (a is ancestor of e). Thus, EG is acyclic.

- 2) **Immutability of parents:** An epoch p is a parent of an epoch e if there is an outgoing edge from p towards e . Edges are only created when inserting e in EG and are never removed. Thus, the parents of an epoch e form an immutable set.

The theorem holds, as both properties hold. \square

Lemma 6. Consider an epoch e and its parent epochs which form the set P . When a node A receives e via an EPOCHDATA message of EGSync, it holds that A inserts e in EG_A if $\nexists e' \in P \wedge e' \notin EG_A$.

Proof. When A processes the EPOCHDATA message, the message handler calls the CHECKAPPLY function (Figure 11, line 15) to insert e in EG_A . In line 4 of Algorithm 5, A successfully inserts e in EG_A , only if $\nexists e' \in P : e' \notin EG_A$ (Algorithm 5, lines 2 - 3). Thus, the Lemma holds. \square

Theorem 7. Consider a node A that receives an epoch e during the execution of EGSync. The following properties of epoch graphs are maintained:

- 1) The parents of epoch e form an immutable set P .
- 2) An epoch graph is single-rooted, connected, directed and acyclic.

Proof.

- 1) **Immutability of parents:** Node A receives e via an EPOCHDATA message, along with set P . The message handlers of EGSync, described in Figures 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, and 12, do not alter the contents of P , and A inserts e in EG_A , if $\nexists e', e' \in P \wedge e' \notin EG_A$ (Lemma 6). Moreover, when e has been inserted in EG_A , neither its existing incoming links can be removed, nor new incoming links are created. Thus, the set P , which form the parent epochs of e is immutable; the execution of EGSync maintains the property.

- 2) **Single-root:**

Private epoch graph: All nodes of a personal group of devices, create an empty epoch re , with a well known identifier eid , for the root epoch of the *private epoch graph*. Thus, all nodes of a user's personal group of devices, create the same single root epoch.

Shared epoch graph: The first time node A, which participates in share S , executes EGSync regarding S successfully, it receives the root epoch re_s of share S . This is the single root epoch, which the creator of S has constructed, and its common across all participants of S for the *shared epoch graph*.

Thus, an epoch graph, either the *private* or a *shared* has a single root.

Connected & directed: Node A receives epoch e only via an EPOCHDATA message. Then, A inserts the received epoch e in EG_A by adding vertex e in the set of vertices of EG_A , and by adding an edge from $e', \forall e' \in P$ towards e to the set of edges of EG_A . P is the set of vertices that form the parents of e , as constructed in the node that created epoch e , and all epochs of P should exist in EG_A to insert e in EG_A , by Lemma 6. Thus, when A inserts a received epoch e in EG_A , EG_A remains connected and directed.

Acyclic: When inserting e in EG, e is becoming leaf. From previous epochs in EG (due to Lemma 6) we draw edges to that leaf node. As the set P (that forms the parent epochs of e) is immutable, and the new epoch e is leaf (has no outgoing) edges EG remains acyclic.

The theorem holds, as both properties hold. \square

c) *Liveness:*

Lemma 8. Consider two nodes I (Initiator) and T (Target) that execute EGSync. For any epochs a and e in EG_T , where a is ancestor of e , and I receives e via an EPOCHDATA message, it holds that I inserts e in EG_I if $a \in EG_I$.

Proof. The Lemma holds due to recursive application of Lemma 6 on set P , that form the parents of epoch e . \square

Lemma 9. Consider two nodes I (Initiator) and T (Target) that execute EGSync, where T sends a POTENTIALLYMISSING message to I announcing a starting set SS , and all epochs in SS exist in EG_I . I discovers any epoch of EG_T not existing in EG_I (at the time that T processed the SYNCINIT message from I) by the end of EGSync's first phase.

Proof. When T sends a POTENTIALLYMISSING message to I , T announces a set of potentially missing epochs from I ; that is the PNK set. We will first show that any epoch of EG_T not existing in EG_I , at the time that T processed the SYNCINIT message from I , exists in PNK .

Consider nt which is the nearest trunk of SS in EG_T , and as nt is trunk, it has no concurrent epochs (siblings in EG_T). nt is ancestor of an epoch $s \in SS$, and as, by assumption, all epochs of SS exist in EG_I , then nt exists in EG_I due to Lemma 8. T populates PNK with all descendants of nt , except for the ancestors of SS , because: 1) $\forall a, a \in \text{ancestors}(SS) \implies a \in EG_I$, by Lemma 8. Furthermore, note that the ancestors of nt are also excluded from PNK , as $\text{ancestors}(nt) \subset \text{ancestors}(SS)$. 2) there are no siblings (concurrent epochs) of nt in EG_T . As a result, PNK includes all epochs of EG_T , except for those which T knows that exist in EG_I . Thus all epochs of EG_T not existing in EG_I , at the time that T processed the SYNCINIT message from I , exist in PNK .

Given that $\nexists e \in EG_T : e \notin EG_I \wedge e \notin PNK$, when I handles the POTENTIALLYMISSING message from T (which is the last incoming message from T for the first phase), I calls the MISSINGEPOCHS function (Figure 9, line 5), and discovers all epochs of EG_T missing from EG_I . This is achieved by iterating PNK (Algorithm 3, line 5) and discovering all epochs not existing in EG_I ; thus the Lemma holds. \square

Lemma 10. Consider two nodes I (Initiator) and T (Target) that execute $EGSync$, where T sends a POTENTIALLYMISSING message to I announcing a starting set SS , and at least one epoch in SS does not exist in EG_I . In this case, I terminates the currently active protocol instance with T , and initiates a new one by sending a SESSIONINIT message to T , with 'current knowledge' set to be the output epoch e of Algorithm 4. For this epoch e it holds that $e \in EG_I \wedge e \in EG_T$.

Proof. We will first show that in Algorithm 4 all epochs inserted in the known set K exist in both EG_I and EG_T . T creates SS when handling the SYNCINIT message from I , using the PNKEPOCHS function (Figure 8, line 3). In line 8 of Algorithm 2 (this is the case that may lead to an epoch s of SS not existing in EG_I), T populates SS with epochs that:

- 1) exist in EG_T ($\forall s, s \in SS \implies s \in EG_T$), and
- 2) are created by a node I' (each epoch $s \in SS$ by a different node I). Each node I' is member of the personal group of devices of user U , with U being the owner of I .

I populates K with epochs that exist in EG_I . These epochs also exist in EG_T ; there are the following two cases and we will show and in both it applies:

- 1) an epoch $k \in K$ inserted in line 5 of Algorithm 4 exists in SS . As k exists in SS , it holds that k also exists in EG_T as described above.
- 2) an epoch $k \in K$ inserted in line 7 of Algorithm 4 exist in EG_T , because k is ancestor of an epoch $s \in SS$, and

Lemma 8 applies. We will now show why any epoch k , inserted in line 7, is an ancestor of an epoch $s \in SS$ by contradiction. Assuming k is not ancestor of s , then k could be concurrent to s , equal to s , or descendant of s .
Case 1: concurrent: Both epochs s and k have been created by the same node (Algorithm 4, line 7); thus s and k are not concurrent epochs (siblings in epoch graph).

Case 2: equal: If it holds that $k = s$, then k would have been inserted in K in line 5, as $s \in EG_T \wedge k \in EG_I$.

Case 3: Descendant: If it holds that k is descendant of s , and because $k \in EG_I$, then $s \in EG_I$ by Lemma 8, and epoch s would have been inserted in K in line 5. As all case are invalid, any epoch k inserted in line 7 is ancestor of an epoch $s \in SS$.

Thus, $\forall k \in K$, k exists in both EG_I and EG_T .

Finally, the Lemma holds because the output e of Algorithm 4 is the nearest trunk of K (Algorithm 4, line 7), all epochs $k \in K$ exist in both EG_I and EG_T , and e exists in both EG_I and EG_T by Lemma 8. \square

Theorem 11. Consider two nodes I (Initiator) and T (Target) that execute $EGSync$. Assuming both I and T do not crash, then I discovers any epoch of EG_T that was not in EG_I at the time T processed the SYNCINIT message from I , in at most two iterations of $EGSync$'s first phase.

Proof. In the first phase of the protocol, T sends a POTENTIALLYMISSING message to I , announcing a starting set SS . When all epochs of SS exist in EG_I , the theorem holds, at the end of the first iteration, due to Lemma 9.

In case that at least one epoch $s \in SS$ does not exist in EG_I , then the session is aborted and a new session is initiated (second iteration of first phase) using the output of Algorithm 4 as current knowledge set (CK). Due to Lemma 10, the single epoch e of CK exists in both EG_I and EG_T . As a result, during the second iteration of $EGSync$'s first phase:

- 1) I sends to T a SESSIONINIT message, announcing CK . Then, given that the single epoch $e \in CK$ exists in EG_T , T creates SS with $SS = CK$ (Algorithm 2, line 10).
- 2) T responds to I with a POTENTIALLYMISSING message, announcing SS . Given that the single epoch $e \in CK$ exists in EG_I , and that $SS = CK$, then all epochs of SS exist in EG_I . Because of this, at the end of the second iteration of the $EGSync$'s first phase, Lemma 9 applies, and the theorem holds.

Thus, the theorem holds in both cases. \square

Theorem 12. Consider two nodes I (Initiator) and T (Target) that execute $EGSync$. Given that, at the end of $EGSync$'s first phase, I discovers the set ME of epochs missing from EG_I , and assuming I does not crash, then I eventually obtains $e, \forall e \in ME$ if either: 1) the original node O that I requested e from remains reachable until it delivers e successfully, or 2) in the case O becomes unreachable, at least one node H hosting e is reachable from I , I initiates a new protocol

instance with H after the failed previous request for e (from I to O) is discovered, and H remains reachable until it delivers e successfully.

Proof. For any epoch $e \in ME$ $EGSync$ works as follows. I requests e either from T via a GETMISSING message, or has already requested e from another node during a concurrent protocol instance. Let O be the node that I has requested e from. Provided that O remains reachable until it delivers e to I (first case of the theorem), then I obtains e from O .

In case O becomes unreachable before replying with e , then the triggered timeout will erase e from *requestedEpochs* (Figure 12, line 7), to allow re-requesting it. Assuming I initiates a new protocol instance with a reachable node H that hosts e , and H remains reachable, then I will obtain e from H during this new instance.

Thus, I receives e , $\forall e \in ME$, either

- 1) from the original node O from which it requested e , or
- 2) eventually from another reachable node H hosting e via a new protocol instance.

□

Theorem 13. Consider two nodes A and B , that execute $EGSync$. Given that 1) both A and B do not crash, and 2) A and B synchronize each other until $EGSync$ discovers no missing epochs, for either node, during the protocol’s first phase, then EG_A is equal to EG_B .

Proof. We assume that nodes A and B , execute $EGSync$ multiple times, with both nodes acquiring the roles of both Initiator (I) and Target(T).

I discovers any missing epoch from a node T during the execution of the first phase of $EGSync$, assuming that both I and T do not crash (Assumption 1), by Theorem 11. Assuming that A and B synchronize each other until $EGSync$ discovers no missing epochs, for either node, during the protocol’s first phase (Assumption 2), then, due to Theorem 11, it holds that:

- $\forall e, e \in EG_A \implies e \in EG_B$
- $\forall e, e \in EG_B \implies e \in EG_A$

Thus, the set of vertices is common for EG_A and EG_B .

Moreover, due to Theorem 7, the parents of each epoch e are immutable, and the edges of epoch graph are created from each parent of e and towards e ; thus the set of incoming edges of e is common for EG_A and EG_B . Given that the set of vertices is common in EG_A and EG_B , and each vertex (epoch) e has the same set of incoming edges in EG_A and EG_B , then the set of edges is common for EG_A and EG_B . Thus, the Theorem holds; EG_A and EG_B are equal because they have:

- the same set of vertices, and
- the same set of edges.

□

Theorem 14. Consider two nodes A and B , that execute $EGSync$. Given that EG_A is equal to EG_B , then A and B have equal metadata repositories.

Proof. Consider the following:

- 1) each file system action that affects the *metadata repository* is recorded in an epoch e , which is inserted in the epoch graph (the *metadata update log*), and
- 2) when an epoch e , which is received via $EGSync$, is inserted in the epoch graph, then its entries update the metadata repository.

As EG_A and EG_B are equal by assumption, and due to the above, nodes A and B have equal *metadata repositories*. Thus, the theorem holds. □

8) *Content Synchronization:* Partial replication of file content is based on user-defined *Replication Rules*. In our current design, these rules specify a directory in the file system, and a set of $\langle Device, latestOnly \rangle$ tuples, specifying to which devices the content of files under that directory and any of its sub-directories should be replicated. The *latestOnly* flag denotes if, at the specific device, the system should replicate the content for the complete history of objects, or only for their latest versions (the leaf nodes of the version graph). The MS maintains a complete registry of which device holds which content element, as devices write in the *update log* an entry each time they add an element to their local CS . Our system design includes a *Replication Rules Enforcer* subsystem, that runs in the background whenever a generation is closed. It uses as input the *Replication Rules*, the object metadata, and the local CS ’s current contents, and produces a) a set of $Cids$ that reside at the local CS and should be removed, and b) a set of $Cids$ that are missing from the current node and should be fetched. The set of missing content is forwarded to a *Content Fetcher* subsystem, that locates devices that possess the content by querying the *metadata repository*’s, and requests from them each missing content item using its Cid . In the case of multiple devices hosting the missing element, *Content Fetcher* selects one based on proximity, as identified by the *Device Management* substrate.

Content to be discarded at device A is first marked for deletion with an entry in the current generation, denoting an “intent to delete” from device A for the specific content element with Cid . Device A then waits for an acknowledgment from another device B , at a later generation, denoting that B owns and “intends to hold” the specific content element. Once A receives that, it proceeds to actually delete the specific content from its local CS , and adds an entry in the *update log* recording this deletion. This mechanism is necessary to avoid having a device immediately delete a locally generated content element, because it does not match its own *Replication Rules*. Instead, with this mechanism (inspired by [12]), a content element is guaranteed to be deleted from a system node only when another node takes custody of it.

9) *Consistency and privacy properties:* The MS , synchronized via our epoch-graph-based synchronization protocol, forms a delta-state Conflict-Free Replicated data type (δ -CRDT, see [13]) and guarantees Strong Eventual Consistency (SEC, [14]). $EGSync$ provides SEC because, provided that all messages are delivered, the MS repository will be identical across all nodes, and a conflict can never occur for the MS

data itself; the only potential conflicts in our system are for user files which are presented to user-space consistently by our *FS* layer. For synchronization of objects in our *CS* (file content), O^3 achieves *Eventual Filter Consistency* (EFC), as defined in [15]. EFC guarantees that if the user defines a replication rule, stating that a set of files S should be replicated to device D , then any file $F \in S$ eventually arrives at device D , provided that messages are delivered.

We observe that our synchronization protocol can be seen as a causally-ordered broadcast channel (see *cbcast* in [16]), where the messages are epochs. Indeed, if an epoch A happened-before epoch E , A will be an ancestor of E in the epoch graph of the specific share. Our *MS* synchronization protocol ensures that A will always be replayed before E , ensuring causal-replay of all dependent epochs. For concurrent epochs, our sync protocol makes no guarantees of ordering. In our *MS* design, this is immaterial, as the worst that can happen is that different children (versions) of a single node in an object’s version graph might be added, at concurrent epochs. In the replay of these epochs, some devices may place one child before the other, while others may do the opposite. However, the order of children in our epoch graphs is not important, and that’s why our *MS* repositories are equal across nodes in our system.

To recap, *EGSync* achieves the following *consistency* properties: 1) The whole *MS* (metadata repository and update-log) for a user’s private and shared files is replicated across all of her own devices. 2) For shared files, Alice’s devices can relay epochs created by Bob to Bob’s devices, which have not yet received them. 3) Strong eventual consistency and causality-preserving replay of update actions for the *MS* repository.

EGSync also achieves the following *privacy* properties: 1) All non-shared user files are stored locally on a user’s personal devices or, in the case of shared files, on the user’s personal devices as well as those of users with which they collaborate; no third party storage infrastructures are involved. 2) Only shared portions of the *MS* are replicated across devices of other users. 3) Sharing of existing files does not expose their version history to other users. 4) By hiding device ids as well as counters used to produce identifiers, a user cannot learn the number of devices used by another user, the specific device she used to create a file version, and the amount of work she performs in other private folders that are not shared. We note that epoch graphs do reveal the number of devices a user uses concurrently, but that is not necessarily equal to the number of devices they own and use, in total.

C. Content Store

The *Content Store* (*CS*) is the subsystem that manages file content at each O^3 node. The *CS* offers the well known POSIX services (create, open, read, write, close, truncate, fsync), as the interface to manage files. However, the *CS* provides copy-on-write semantics for files. If a file identified by *Cid* c is opened for writing, the *CS* guarantees that the original remains unchanged, and a new *Cid* c' is generated pointing to the new version.

Our design allows for multiple *CS* implementations that are interchangeable. For brevity, we only present the *BackChainCS* here.

BackChainCS is a copy-on-write approach, inspired by [17], where content of versions of the same object (file) forms a chain of modifications, where each entry in the chain contains only data written for this version. If any node of the chain is opened for reading, it may need to route the read request to previous versions in the chain, potentially all the way to the root node, until a node is found that contains the data for the specified range.

Back-chaining is a perfect match for the arbitrary version graphs of the *MS*. This is because new versions of a specific content can be produced concurrently at different devices, at a fork of the file object’s version graph. Since back-chaining does not modify the previous content, all newer (forked) versions of the content can refer to the same parent content without a problem. Thus, in our case, the chain is in fact a directed acyclic graph of content files, where each entry points to exactly one parent node. The DAG of *Cid* back-chaining is potentially different from the DAG of the version graph of the corresponding object. This is because the version graph tracks changes to all metadata entries (not only the *Cid*), while the graph of *Cid* dependencies is drawn based on open for write requests made by the file system.

D. The O^3 File System

Overview. O^3 is the file system that wraps the *MS* and the *CS*, and provides a standard mechanism to interface with them to any application, following standard POSIX semantics. O^3 organizes file objects “inside” directory objects, by setting a metadata attribute for each file object denoting the *Oid* of its host directory. Thus, directories in our design are not catalogs of names and pointers (such as *i-nodes*), but are virtually organized by querying the *MS metadata repository* (as in [18]). When O^3 is presented with a path from the OS kernel, it parses the path element by element, until it locates the final directory. To locate elements (files or directories) inside a directory with *Oid* *HID*, it invokes a function which we call `getDirectoryContents`. It starts with the root directory of the filesystem which has a fixed *Oid*, looks for an object with name equal to the first part of the path, and repeats this for every element of the path. Algorithm 6 presents the pseudocode and outlines (at a very high level) how O^3 utilizes the *MS* to access the objects it manages. Additionally, O^3 utilizes the *CS* to service file read and write operations.

In Algorithm 6, the `setOfObjects()` function (line 4) returns the set of unique objects found in its input, the `leaves()` function (line 6) produces the list of leaves of the version graph of a specific object, while the `decorate()` function (lines 9, 10) produces a file name that includes extra information, such as the object and version identifiers (demonstrated below). Function `commonParent()` (line 10) locates the version that is the common parent of a list of versions, using the levels assigned by Algorithm 1. Function `processCrossObjectNamingConflicts()` (line 12)

Algorithm 6 Get Directory Contents

```
1: function GETDIRECTORYCONTENTS(HID):    ▷ returns set of names
2:   r = {}                                ▷ the set to return
3:   V = MS.lookup(hostId = HID, isLeaf = True)
4:   for each o in setOfObjects(V) do
5:     ov = MS.getVersions(o)
6:     lv = leaves(ov)
7:     if lv.count > 1 then
8:       for each n in lv do
9:         r += decorate(n)
10:      r += decorate(commonParent(lv))
11:     else
12:       r += n.name
return processCrossObjectNamingConflicts(r)
```

iterates over the given set, finds names shared between two or more objects, and decorates them.

Conflict management. Because O^3 supports unmodified applications, it cannot assume anything from them regarding conflict management, but has to provide a universal interface for conflict presentation and resolution. In O^3 , there are two categories of conflicts: same object metadata and/or content conflicts, and cross object naming conflicts. When the `getDirectoryContents` service is invoked for a directory, O^3 obtains all objects with at least one leaf version residing in the specific directory (lines 3-4). For each such object, O^3 checks if multiple leaf versions are active (lines 5-7), thus identifying all same-object conflicts. After that, the `getDirectoryContents` service detects cross object naming conflicts (line 13) by searching for duplicate file names in a directory listing with different object identifiers.

In O^3 , multiple concurrent independent operations in the same directory (e.g., creation of two files with different names) do not generate conflicts. This is because of our design choice to store the host directory as metadata for each object's version, thus obviating the need to store a physical directory object with name to i-node assignments. Moreover, as a deletion in O^3 results in the creation of a new version, remove/update conflicts become equivalent to update/update conflicts (using the terminology from [19]).

For cross-object naming conflicts, O^3 *decorates* the file name of each conflicting version with the object identifier and the version identifier. For same-object conflicts, O^3 includes in the directory listing each conflicting version (lines 8-9), not necessarily residing in the specific directory, again using *decorated* file names. Additionally, O^3 presents one more entry for the non-leaf version that is the common parent (line 10) of all listed leaf versions. To locate the common parent, we leverage our *level-ranking* algorithm and locate the trunk node with level equal to the level of any leaf version minus one, with a simple depth-first search from any leaf. Without the level ranking algorithm, O^3 would have to use more costly graph traversal algorithms to detect the nearest common ancestor. This last entry, which is also listed *decorated*, can help user-space tools perform a three-way merge of the common parent and the conflicting versions.

For all conflicting versions, O^3 adds comments in the decoration of file names, aiding the user to identify the changes

in the specific version. Comments report the type of conflict (change in permissions, move/rename, change in content etc), the device in which the conflicting versions were created and the original location of artificial entries. Artificial entries are those not residing in the current directory, but listed due to move/update or move/move conflicts with their siblings. This action is executed dynamically, as full file paths could change at any component of the path.

To clarify what a decorated name is, consider the following examples:

1) A file named `notes.txt` is present in the root folder and is in conflict because of concurrent modifications to its content. When the user issues “`ls notes*`” at the mount point of O^3 , she will get back something like the following (simplified for brevity):

```
notes.txt;123@1#common-parent
notes.txt;123@2#content change at DevA
notes.txt;123@3#content change at DevB
```

2) A directory `dirA` and a file named `notes.txt` are present in the root folder. A move/update conflict is created when `notes.txt` is both modified and moved to directory `dirA` concurrently at two different devices. When the user issues “`ls notes*`” at the mount point of O^3 , she will get back something like the following:

```
notes.txt;123@1#common-parent
notes.txt;123@2#content change at DevA
notes.txt;123@3#move at DevB, located at /dirA
```

Moreover, if the user issues “`ls dirA/notes*`”, she will get back the same set of entries, with differences only in the comments designating the location of each version. In both cases, any attempt to access a file named `notes.txt` will fail, and the user will have to access any of the above *decorated* names to view the corresponding information (data or metadata). These entries allow any user-space tool that supports three-way merge to access the above “files” and provide a user-friendly merge experience. The examples above depict versions with `Vids` 1, 2, and 3, of an object with `Oid` 123. The user can *extend* either of the conflicting versions (besides the common parent), with further edits, until the conflict is resolved. At this point, she chooses one version as the correct one and instructs O^3 to mark it as the conflict resolution. O^3 creates a new version with parents all the current leaf versions, and sets its metadata equal to the chosen one; now the file `notes.txt` (undecorated) becomes available again for access.

O^3 fully supports files with decorated names. They are listed in the directory, and any attempt to open and read one such file yields the content of the specific version. Additionally, an attempt to modify a file with a decorated name, results in the generation of a new version that extends the specific “branch” for the object's version graph with a new leaf node.

O^3 supports any *concurrent combination* of the above conflict categories uniformly and consistently. A user can move the same file to different directories, perform edits, move it again, and keep editing, concurrently on different devices. When the user locates any leaf version of a file object in a

directory, she will receive a listing of all leaf nodes, decorated with comments about their differences. She will then be able to resolve all of these conflicts by choosing to “keep” one of these versions, potentially after further editing it to incorporate edits from other versions. For example, assume the root directory of a user has the following objects: `dirA`, `dirB`, and `notes.txt`. A concurrent move, from two different devices, of `notes.txt` to folders `dirA` and `dirB` respectively, that could also be followed by any number of edits, will result in a “location conflict” of `notes.txt`. In O^3 , all versions (the common parent and the two leaves) will be visible on both folders. This example applied on a system that does not track per-object history (such as DropBox, ownCloud, Ori, etc) will result in two different files `notes.txt` on both folders `dirA` and `dirB`, without detection of any conflict. Concluding, unlike prior systems, O^3 can detect and report *any combination of concurrent actions* that could create a conflict in the system.

Open file sharing across applications. O^3 includes logic to handle new files and to facilitate application cooperation in the face of file versioning. To this end, O^3 maintains an *OpenFiles* data structure indexed by path name for new files, and $\langle \text{Oid}, \text{Vid} \rangle$ for existing files. Whenever a file is created because of a kernel request, O^3 asks the CS to create a new content element, registers the file into *OpenFiles* (with full metadata filled), and routes all further accesses to the specific full path name to this entry of *OpenFiles*. Additionally, whenever a version of a file is opened, and while it remains open, all accesses to the specific file name are routed to the same object, again via the *OpenFiles* structure. This allows shared access to files and, thus application cooperation as per the UNIX philosophy.

Fetch-on-demand. O^3 supports *fetch-on-demand* for missing files. If a device, because of its replication rules, is missing the content of a file, O^3 forwards a request to the Content Fetcher subsystem. The Content Fetcher identifies devices that own the content, and routes the request to the closest device. Once the content is fetched, O^3 is notified and delivers it to the kernel.

Special folders for accessing the full version graph. O^3 exposes two special, hidden directories at the root of its mount point. The first is `.history`, which allows access to the full history recorded by the *MS*. In fact, because of *fetch-on-demand*, even on devices where the replication rules dictate receiving only the latest versions of files, the user can still view previous versions of files, as their content is fetched automatically upon access.

The second special folder is `.snapshot`, via which O^3 exposes all snapshots taken by the user, using their name as a directory name. When the user changes directory into one of these snapshots, she gets a view of the file system as it was when the snapshot was taken. O^3 supports *snapshots* of the entire file system, or of a specific set of directories. Whenever a snapshot is taken, O^3 creates a snapshot object that records *MS*’s current generation vector *GV* that encapsulates the knowledge of the device’s currently open generation. The snapshot object is a first class object in

MS, one that is replicated across all devices, making the snapshot universal. The `getDirectoryContents` service, when invoked for a specific snapshot, responds with entries that were valid up to and including the specific recorded *GV*, in other words presents older versions in the version graph as the leaf versions. To implement this, O^3 ignores generations with concurrent generation vectors (which correspond to changes that happened concurrently at other devices at snapshot time), and uses the less than operator for *GVs* that are comparable, to filter out newer data.

Data cleanup. Finally, O^3 supports data cleanup operations for individual files. It provides services to delete the entire history of a file, or a specific version of a file. Deletion of a file’s version updates the version graph accordingly to eliminate the deleted node, and dereferences the deleted version’s *Cid*. If the *Cid* (at the *MS*) reaches a reference count of zero, it is deleted from the *CS* as well. Each *CS* implementation is required to support deletion of a specific *Cid*. Data cleanup can help reduce the size of both the *MS* repository (of object metadata), and the *CS* storage area (of file content).

E. Extra functionality beyond the VFS interface

The O^3 user-space program is a tool we created to provide extra functionality for O^3 , one that is not possible when constrained behind the kernel VFS interface. The O^3 tool supports the commands listed in Table I. The `rrule` command allows adding, deleting, and listing replication rules. The `snapshot` command allows the user to take or discard a snapshot. The `conflicts` command lists all conflicts currently existing across the entire file system. The `resolve` command, helps resolve a conflict in the system, by instructing O^3 to keep only one of the leaf versions and make it supersede a specific set of its sibling leaf nodes (closing at least one of the forks). The `forget` command allows the user to purge either a specific version from the version graph, or an object’s entire version graph from the *MS*. The `share` and `mount` commands allows the user to create a share or mount in the local system shares of other users. Finally, the `find` command allows the user to list the devices storing the content of a particular file.

Command	Description
<code>rrule</code>	allows management of replication rules
<code>snapshot</code>	allows management of snapshots
<code>conflicts</code>	lists all conflicts in the filesystem
<code>resolve</code>	allows user to resolve conflicts
<code>forget</code>	allows user to purge the <i>MS</i>
<code>share</code>	allows user to create and list shares
<code>mount</code>	allows user to mount shares of other users
<code>find</code>	allows user to list devices storing a particular file

Table I: List of O^3 commands

F. Consistency among devices

Our metadata synchronization algorithm forms a delta-state Conflict-Free Replicated data type (δ -CRDT, see [13]) that achieves Strong Eventual Consistency [14] for our *MS*. That is, a conflict can never occur for the *MS* data itself;

the only potential conflicts in our system are for user files. For synchronization of objects in our CS (file content), O^3 achieves *Eventual Filter Consistency* (EFC), as defined in [15]. EFC guarantees that if the user defines a replication rule, stating that a set of files S should be replicated to device D , then any file $F \in S$ eventually arrives at device D .

V. CRASH-FAULT TOLERANCE IN O^3

As a filesystem, O^3 must ensure the consistency of the stored files in the presence of crashes. This involves both meta-data and actual file data. We leave file data consistency to the application, by forwarding the `fsync` system call through O^3 and CS, to the underlying file system hosting the file content (typically ext4). Thus, in this section, we focus on metadata consistency in O^3 . We first describe how we guarantee that the MS data store remains consistent in the event of crash faults. We then give an overview of how we ensure that files modified but not yet closed do not get lost in the event of a crash.

A. MS consistency

To ensure the consistency of the MS data store, O^3 utilizes a checkpointing mechanism, using multiple data and journal files. Our approach is analogous to [20], but instead of being application-agnostic, it is designed specifically for O^3 and our copy-on-write paging mechanism we describe below.

An *checkpoint period* is the period between two checkpoints, and is identified by an ever increasing number e . The in-memory data store is logically a single contiguous memory region, but it is physically spread across multiple data files, at the system page size granularity. We again use sparse-files for the data files, as for the `BackChainCS`. When the system starts, the first data file is mapped to memory and contains the whole data store. At checkpoint time, a new data file is created and mapped to memory. After the checkpoint, any data page of the data store that is modified is first copied from the original data file to the new. We keep a memory resident index of the physical address of each page, as a means to quickly locate the “active” page. Each data file is identified as $D[e]$.

We additionally use a journal that logs all high level data store update operations that MS processes. We do not `fsync` the journal file, so we rely on the OS to persist the changes to disk periodically, exactly as a journal file is implemented in contemporary journaling file systems like ext4. We break down the journal into multiple physical files, one for each *checkpoint period* (identified by $J[p]$).

The system terminates the current checkpoint period by creating a checkpoint, as described in Algorithm 7. This algorithm spawns a slow background process (`writeToDisk`), while the foreground work is fast. As such, the system may safely have multiple checkpoints persisting data to disk at the same time. Once a checkpoint for a period is completed, the matching journal is erased. On startup, the system treats the data file of any checkpoint period with an existing journal file as corrupted. For such a period, it discards and recreates the corresponding data file, and replays the journal.

Algorithm 7 Checkpoint

```

1: procedure CHECKPOINT
2:   close(J[p])
3:   p = p + 1
4:   create(D[p])
5:   mapToMemory(D[p])
6:   create(J[p])
7:   async: writeToDisk(p - 1)
8:   procedure WRITETODISK( $i$ )
9:     msync(D[i])
10:    unlink(J[i])

```

While this approach guarantees MS data store consistency, it creates a series of data files with duplicated pages, thus wasting space. To efficiently clean up old data files and merge all active data pages in one data file, we periodically use a *compact* background task which runs at a lower priority than the file system. This task starts from the oldest existing data file (say $D[o]$) and copies all its active pages (i.e., the ones not overwritten in later checkpoint periods) to the current checkpoint period’s data file $D[p]$. When the next checkpoint finishes and thus $D[p]$ is safely persisted to disk, $D[o]$ is deleted from disk, as all its pages can now be found at $D[p]$. The compact background task repeats this process for each active data file $D[i]$ for i in o to $p - 1$. If the system crashes before the checkpoint completes, no data file is deleted, $D[p]$ will be discarded, and the compact background task will repeat the same data page copying from scratch, until $D[p]$ successfully persists and the old data files are deleted.

B. Preserving new files and versions

As explained in Section III, O^3 first creates a file for a new object or version in the CS, and only when the file is closed its metadata is registered in the MS. Thus, in the event of a system crash, there may be files in the CS that will be inaccessible. To address this, we implement a Recovery Manager (RM) that stores all information about new files/versions in a recovery journal (RJ). Upon creation of a new *cid*, the CS accepts a token that is registered at RJ along with the *cid*, as a new entry. This token is generated by the MS and includes all information known by MS at the time (such as `oid`, `vid`, file name, etc). At system initialization, the RM reads RJ (if present) and for each entry, it notifies the MS with the `cid` and the token, allowing MS to properly register the `cid` or ask the CS to discard it.

VI. DISCUSSION

A. Conflict presentation

We chose to address conflicts in the manner described in Section IV-D, because we believe the rules are clear and only files in conflict need caution when accessed. In the examples given, the file in conflict named `notes.txt` must be accessed via a decorated name, while all other non-conflicting files are fully accessible. Moreover, we present conflicts early on upon detection, but still allow the user to continue working on one “branch” of the conflicting version history. Thus, the

user can postpone conflict resolution for a more convenient time, *at any device*, without risking data loss.

This conflict naming scheme is ideal for documents but potentially cumbersome for application specific files, as the user may be completely unaware of their existence (such as configuration files). For the latter case, O^3 could provide a different naming scheme, where one version of the file retains its name. However, such an approach, which is basically hiding the conflict, could delay or completely obstruct the detection of conflicts by the user, with unknown consequences for consistency.

Another option for managing conflicts for such “hidden” files, would be to modify the application to support O^3 . Such a customization would simply need an extra step when a file is reported missing; that is, to look for decorated versions of the file name and take different actions than if the file did not exist. This step would be implemented with the `opendir/readdir` system calls. After that, the application may take a range of actions. It can simply report the detected conflict immediately and ask the user to resolve it. It can also merge the contents of the different versions dynamically, if possible, and progress normally. Finally, it can automatically resolve the conflict, by invoking the O^3 tool with `fork/exec`.

We emphasize that customizing an application for O^3 does not require linking the application with a custom library. Thanks to our POSIX-compliance and our well-defined naming convention, applications can be customized by simply enumerating the files in a directory and taking actions based on the ones they find. For developers who choose to customize their applications, O^3 becomes a middleware component that handles file synchronization and replication, and allows the upper-layer (the application) to manage the conflicts if and when they occur.

B. Accidental Deletion Protection

O^3 helps protect the users from themselves in the case of accidental deletion of data. Suppose that a user accidentally deletes files she does not intend to delete. In any cloud service solution, this deletion would propagate to the server, and from the server to all devices. Some cloud services maintain the deleted files, if they were present on the server, for a specified retention period. Still, the user must realize her error soon enough and within this retention period.

O^3 , in contrast, preserves the full history of all files, at all times, without the user having to issue commands. Thus, the user can always look into the `.history` folder for older versions of files, regardless of time of deletion. The only way to prune the history in O^3 is explicitly, by invoking the O^3 tool and instructing it to *forget* the deleted files. This makes accidental data loss a two-step process, which is safer than the single-step deletion of other systems.

VII. IMPLEMENTATION

We implement the prototype of O^3 using C++ on Linux. We use 64-bit identifiers for all objects in the system; we encode in them the device using 4 bits, the user using 12

bits (which is locally translated from the text representation using a dictionary), and use the remaining 48 bits for a number that gets assigned from counters. This 64-bit size is an implementation choice, which can easily scale to 128-bits and more, as needed.

For the *MS*, we employ a custom data store (DS) using memory-mapped files, copy-on-write mechanisms for checkpointing, and an implementation of B+tree for dictionaries, such as the contents of directories.

The DS maps a sparse data file in memory and provides a memory manager abstraction for allocating and deallocating portions of it. It expects a notification before the calling application modifies any region, with which we implement copy-on-write. O^3 uses the DS to store all object, version, and epoch data. Sparse files are files with missing data ranges, where these ranges are artificially considered to be filled with zeroes. Sparse files are supported by all major contemporary file systems (ext4, ZFS, NTFS, APFS). We also use a journal to record all high-level DS mutating actions, and DS provides for checkpoints where a new data file and journal file are allocated. Upon checkpoint, O^3 is free to continue immediately, while asynchronously the previous data file is flushed to disk and the previous journal file is deleted. Upon startup, any existing journal files are replayed to ensure consistency of our data files. We employ this design so that there is no `fsync` call in the hot-path of the *FS*’s operations, allowing us to gain the performance demonstrated in the benchmarks.

For our *CS* implementation, the `BackChainCS` we also use *sparse* files for preserving disk space. The `BackChainCS` preserves space by creating a “hole” at the new content file, and filling it in at a disk block size accuracy (typically 4KB). It serves reads for written blocks from the current version, and recursively consults previous (back-chained) content versions to serve blocks not written in the current session. To achieve this, it builds a chain of content files, using symbolic links. We manage this back-chaining without any disk space overhead for bookkeeping information at the individual content file level, by using the ability of the `lseek` system call to report data ranges in sparse files. As file systems track data ranges at the block level (and not at the byte-offset level), whenever a portion of a block is written, we visit the chain until we locate the previous version of the specific block, and fill in the remainder of the data until the block is full, at which point we write the completed block in the current content file.

We implement the *FS* over FUSE. Implementations compatible with FUSE exist for both Microsoft Windows and Apple Mac OS, giving us confidence about the portability of O^3 . Furthermore, we recognize that the *FS* is simply one interface to O^3 , and different interfaces exist for mobile platforms, such as the Android Storage Access Framework (SAF) and the iOS FileProvider framework. To this end, we have an ongoing project underway to port O^3 to Android by implementing a SAF provider as its interface, demonstrating that O^3 is portable to all major mobile and desktop platforms.

For our asynchronous communications layer, we employ a messaging backend in C++ which abstracts away all node con-

nectivity issues, and manages message submission, delivery, and presence notifications. The network interfacing part of O^3 is implemented using event handlers. In the prototype we use for the evaluation in this work, we use direct TCP connections and configuration files to manage node discovery. We describe our work to allow connectivity of users across the Internet in a separate article [21].

VIII. EVALUATION

We experimentally evaluate O^3 to gauge its scaling potential to support offline collaboration. We also conduct file system micro benchmarks to demonstrate that O^3 's performance is comparable to the state-of-the-art, when used as a local (versioning) filesystem. We conduct our experiments using a cluster of 7 machines, connected over a Gigabit Ethernet switch. They comprise Octa-core Intel Xeon E5-2620v4 @ 2.10GHz, 32GB RAM, and two 300GB SAS disks, running CentOS 7 Linux. To select workloads that reflect real use cases, the members of our team recorded the file operations inside their home directories, for an aggregated period of one month, using Linux's *inotify* service. We use the recorded traces to select the parameters of the Filebench experiment (presented below), and to create a synthetic mixed workload (with both read and write operations) for O^3 's scaling experiments. For the network experiments, we simulate a WAN environment by using netem [22], to inject a uniform latency of 50ms for each network packet exchanged. For all experiments we report an average of 3 runs, where standard deviation among runs is reported when higher than 5%.

Benchmark	O^3	Loopback	Ori
create	16951.23	22657.43 \pm 7.33%	19121.08
delete	13331.92	6462.4	4729.69
listdirs	6428.44	7598.44 \pm 13.35%	6748.77
makedirs	11109.97	3422.13	11910.47
removedirs	12498.77	218.29	14093.73
stat	35770.67	26483.39	42897.71 \pm 10.18%

Table II: Filebench Microbenchmarks. Creation, deletion and stat of 200,000 files and creation, deletion and listing of 200,000 directories in a directory tree, reported in ops/sec.

Micro Benchmarks. We use Filebench [23] to compare O^3 with Loopback (Ext4 over FUSE), as the base of a file system's performance when operating under FUSE, and Ori [24], a state-of-the-art multi-device, fully replicated file system. We report the results in Table II. Both O^3 and Ori outperform Loopback in creation and deletion of directories, since they do not create physical directories but update their data structures, while in listing of files they use cached file metadata. Ori outperforms O^3 in the latter, as it caches whole file paths instead of file names, thus achieving constant lookup time. However, this design choice does not allow rename operations. In the deletion of files, O^3 outperforms the remaining systems because it does not delete the actual content, as per its versioning semantics, and it simply registers a new file version denoting the operation. In the remaining results (create, listdirs, stat) the systems show comparable

performance, taking into account the high standard deviation among runs for Loopback and Ori. Note that, whenever a file is modified and closed, O^3 creates a new version, in contrast to the remaining systems. Ori's versioning functionality is triggered only when the user takes a snapshot of the file system as a whole; thus while Filebench is running it does not track any versions at all.

I/O performance. We conduct this experiment to evaluate the impact our design has on file I/O performance of the FS, by performing a mix of read, write and rewrite operations, using Bonnie++ [25]. In this experiment, we compare O^3 with LoopbackFH and Ori. Figure 13 presents the results and shows that O^3 performance is on a par with LoopbackFH and Ori, even though O^3 's CS performs Copy-On-Write.

Figure 13: Bonnie++ experiment. We measure file I/O throughput for O^3 , LoopbackFH, and Ori.

Size of repository. To demonstrate the low space overhead of O^3 , we measure the actual disk space needed to store both data and metadata, when the system is populated with the home directory of one of the co-authors, with a total size of 39GB (5,608 directories with 27,723 files where 3GB are documents, 1GB source code, and 35GB media). We compare O^3 with Ori and Wayback. We mount each file system, copy the data inside, and measure the actual space occupied. For O^3 , we measure MS, CS and recovery journal. All systems occupy the same total disk space of approximately 39GB (ext4: 39,650MB, O^3 : 39,654MB, Ori: 39,278MB, Wayback: 39,775MB). Ori gains from data compression 1.1GB, but consumes most of the gain for metadata and indexes. O^3 uses only 25 MB for the MS (which encapsulates the full directory hierarchy) and the recovery journal and thus, imposes a total storage overhead of only 4MB (compared to ext4, that consumes space for directory i-nodes).

Versioning experiment. With this experiment we measure the impact of maintaining versions for a single file, comparing O^3 with Ori and Wayback. We measure the time it takes to append 10KB of data to a text file 1000 times, each time creating a new version of the file. On Ori, this requires manually taking a snapshot after closing every changed file. Wayback (0.03 sec) outperforms O^3 (0.05 sec), because it is

	O^3	LoopbackFH	Ori	Wayback
Time (min)	5.08	3.05	3.8	32.03

Table III: User Workload Experiment. Time (in minutes, lower is better) to replay a month-long user trace.

a single machine versioning system. In contrast, O^3 maintains more information to manage conflicts and synchronization across devices. O^3 performs faster than Ori (92.89 sec) as a full version tracking system.

User workload experiment. To measure the overhead (in time) imposed by versioning, we replay the recorded file system actions, from our user monitoring study, and perform a trace-driven execution on O^3 , LoopbackFH, Ori, and Wayback. The workload consists of 307K read file operations, 16K create file operations, 291K file rewrite operations, 300k delete file operations, 45K move file operations, 32K make directory operations and 184K read directory operations. Table III shows the time required to replay the trace. As expected, Ori is close to LoopbackFH as its versioning functionality is not triggered. In contrast, O^3 creates a new file version for each of the 690K write, rewrite, delete and move operations. This shows that O^3 would impose an overhead of only 1.28 minutes, over a month-long period of usage, to maintain a version for *every* file modification in a user’s home directory, when compared with Ori that does no version tracking whatsoever. As shown in the versioning experiment above, Ori would perform considerably worse if it took frequent snapshots. Finally, Wayback performs considerably slower.

O^3 MS performance. In this set of experiments, we evaluate the performance of the MS’s in-memory implementation.

First, we show that O^3 incurs negligible cost for checkpoints. We repeat our user trace replay, while performing a checkpoint every N seconds. We vary N from 20 secs to 3 mins, with a step of 20 secs. The highest overhead observed from our continuous checkpointing was only 1.4%.

Next, we evaluate how O^3 performs without having its memory-mapped file loaded into memory (cold start), versus having it loaded (warmed-up). We initialize O^3 with a data set of 240K file and directory versions, that reflects the directory hierarchy needed for the replay of the user workload of the previous experiment, and then we measure the time it takes to complete 3 different workloads, one mixed (40% reads - 60% writes), and two synthetic experiments: mostly reads (80% reads - 20% writes) and mostly writes (20% reads - 80% writes). The mixed workload is the recorded trace of the user workload experiment. The synthetic experiments are based on the recorded trace and have the same total number of file system operations as the initial trace. For the warmed-up case, we execute the workload immediately after the initialization workload, while for the cold start case we unmount the system after the initialization workload, clear the OS buffer caches, remount O^3 (without loading the mmapped file in memory) and then execute the workload. Figure 14 shows the execution time, in minutes. We observe a reasonable overhead for the

cold start case, making it a viable mode of operation.

Figure 14: Time to complete three workloads with cold start and warmed-up.

Figure 15: We first measure the time to replay a mixed workload in the file system, when distributing the file I/O operations on multiple shares (blue). We then measure the time to synchronize the whole MS in a WAN setting (red).

Share’s performance. We now measure the performance of O^3 when a user performs file I/O on multiple shares, and plot the results in Figure 15. In the first experiment, we measure the time to execute a mixed workload of 1.2 million file operations (approx. 60% writes/deletes and 40% reads), while distributing them evenly across multiple shares. This workload is the result of recording all file accesses to the home directories of the computers of several members of our research team, for an aggregated period of one month, and thus represent a real world usage scenario.

Recall that the operations of each share are recorded in different EGs. We observe that O^3 ’s performance is not affected by the number of EGs it manages in the MS *update log* (blue line in the figure). In the second experiment, we synchronize a second node with all metadata updates. While the total number of updates is the same, more synchronization

sessions are required when increasing the number of shares (one synchronization session per share), which O^3 handles with sub-linear performance overhead (red line in the figure).

Figure 16: We measure metadata synchronization time in a WAN setting, for a mixed workload distributed evenly across multiple users, when each user initiates a synchronization session to everyone else.

Next, we measure the scaling of *EGSync* when multiple users collaborate concurrently offline. We create one share, we evenly distribute the mixed workload of the previous experiment to n users, we replay the portion of the workload at the corresponding users, and then measure the time it takes for all users to concurrently obtain each other’s work. Each user initiates a synchronization session to every other user in the share, resulting in $n \times (n - 1)$ concurrent synchronization sessions in the network. Assuming we have a workload of size s uniformly distributed across a total number of users n , each user creates updates of size s/n that are propagated to $n - 1$ users resulting in a total load of $s \times (n - 1)$ on the network. Consequently, when increasing the number of users, more data is transferred over the network. Additionally, we note that this is a worst-case scenario, where all users perform a bulk of work concurrently and then they all attempt to synchronize simultaneously. In Figure 16 we observe that, even in this worst case, O^3 scales linearly when synchronizing multiple users concurrently, as expected. Note that, to implement this experiment we used 7 physical nodes each running up to 4 instances of O^3 . Numbers are accurate since disk I/O does not affect our measurements in this experiment. Also note that we repeated this experiment without WAN simulation but numbers were almost identical, hence we omitted them for brevity. Our synchronization protocol is mostly one-way and thus latency has minimal effect in this experiment; only bandwidth is important.

IX. RELATED WORK

Public and Private Cloud Storage. Popular cloud storage providers ([1]–[4]) offer a number of convenient features such

as storage, anytime-anywhere access, automated file synchronization, storage maintenance. Unfortunately, these features come with a significant privacy cost, as users inevitably hand over to the provider their data, or/and their social and working links to other users. Moreover, users may unexpectedly lose their data in case their vendors go out of business [26], or decide to erase old data without warning [8]. Private cloud systems such as ownCloud [27] and network-attached storage products (e.g., [28], [29], [30]) deploy a private server where the user’s data are stored. Such systems avoid the privacy risks of public cloud storage, but are centralized and thus exhibit single points of failure. In addition, they cannot take advantage of opportunistic peer-to-peer connections between devices, instead requiring devices to have continuous connectivity to the private server and to synchronize through the server. They also offer limited support for sharing amongst multiple users, with minimal to no support for conflict detection and resolution. They also limit the number of files that can be stored to the capacity of the private server. Finally, the user shoulders the burden of configuring and maintaining the server.

Versioning Systems. Fossil [31], Venti [32], Elephant [33], Wayback [34] and VersionFS [17] support versioning on a single machine and thus never face conflicts, while O^3 supports versioning across different devices and users and provides additional services such as replication and conflict management.

Lazy replication systems. Several systems support lazy, or optimistic, replication including Perspective [35], Cymbiosis [15], Practi [36], Ori [24], Eyo [37], and IMDfs [11]).

Perspective and Cimbiosys support cross-device data management for a single user’s data collection. They support partial replication and synchronize data by utilizing user-defined rules. Perspective is a FUSE-based file system, while Cimbiosys is a distributed storage system. Unlike O^3 , these systems do not provide a global, unified view of all files nor do they fetch files on demand. Moreover, their design is based on flat, non-hierarchical name spaces, making it infeasible to support the bulk of contemporary Oses. In contrast, O^3 provides a hierarchical namespace, and thus can be deployed now to support all major mobile and desktop platforms. Moreover, Cimbiosys requires at least one device to hold the user’s entire data collection, while O^3 does not.

Eyo and IMDfs support partial replication of a user’s data across devices using user-defined rules. O^3 has a “metadata-everywhere” model similar to that of these systems; i.e., O^3 replicates its metadata store across all devices. However, Eyo is a storage system (not a file system), and as such, requires all applications to be modified to use it. While Eyo provides a global view of all files, it does so at the cost of treating all objects in isolation (via a flat, non-hierarchical organization). Additionally, both Eyo and IMDfs use synchronization protocols based on version vectors that are not designed to provide support for sharing amongst users in a privacy-preserving manner, thus rendering them single-user solutions. In contrast, O^3 ’s epoch-graph-based synchronization protocol is designed to be used across devices of different users without revealing

information about a user's devices or the progress she makes in her own device group.

Ori is a fully replicated distributed file system that synchronizes data between devices. Ori depends heavily on techniques used in Git [38], a distributed version control system. Ori requires full replication of the data repository across all devices and as a result, cannot integrate space-limited devices (such as smartphones) nor can it support distributed storage whose aggregated capacity is greater than any single device. Moreover, Ori enforces early conflict resolution to restrict users from maintaining inconsistencies on different devices. In contrast, O^3 supports *both* partial replication of data to integrate space-limited devices *and* provides a global, unified view of both shared and non-shared (private) files, and allows users to resolve conflicts when convenient.

Several systems have provided a subset of the features of O^3 , in various contexts, such as AFS [39], Ficus [40], Coda [41], Bayou [42], EnsembleBlue [43], Anzere [44], Podbase [45]. However, none provides the full functionality of O^3 . O^3 provides a holistic solution that integrates support for a single user's cross-device personal data management with support for sharing and collaboration with other users, each with their own set of personal devices and needs.

X. CONCLUSIONS

Many critical Internet services on which users depend are controlled by centralized corporate entities, leading users to trade in their privacy (data or/and affiliations with others) for service. O^3 allows users to build private storage clouds for decentralized collaboration with each other, without having to relinquish their data or affiliations to third parties. Our evaluation shows that O^3 's novel *EGSync* protocol, providing causally-consistent replay of changes across devices and across users, can reasonably scale to support collaboration of users in a completely decentralized manner, without the need for intervention and prying eyes of a third party. Future work includes investigating how O^3 could serve as a foundation on which to build other applications and systems, including decentralized social networks, blogging platforms, and multimedia communication applications.

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